

A Study of Administrative Aptitude of Head Teachers of Primary School

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1. Introduction

The journey of human development is full of changes from the ancient age to the age of Internet. It is because of the education is the process, which changes came over very fast in the all kind of sphere of life. The spread of education is increased day by day throughout the world and it is very necessary at every stage of our life. The development of human being is due to education. Thus, education is a basic tool to achieve the expected goal. Stressing the importance of education Dr. Gunavant says, "Life is always full of motion. Development and restructure are a nature of man's life. According to the principles of evolution, in place of stability change and regeneration is the only fact of the universe. And education is one of the factors of this regeneration. Thus, keeping in mind the demand of the future, it is necessary to bring a change in education by removing the errors and making it target oriented and productive. Education is a life –long process going on during man's life. Today's education is child centered. Education gives children opportunities to develop their creative ability and to reach to the depth of it. Different syllabuses of schools have stimulated the cleverness and intelligence of the students. This intelligence of the students helps them to develop their thinking ability and logical ability.

A person can be expert in one or more than one matters very easily. Aptitude is a hidden strength of a person. And this strength is not yet developed. But it can be developed through proper training. If a person gets proper training in proper field, he will go ahead. So, it is our duty to provide them all the equipment's which develop their logical ability. That is how the bad elements like violence, aggressiveness and escapism from the children and they can be diverted to a constructive path and enjoy life. Thus, all these things are centered round the logical aptitude of the child. Today, in the present era of globalization through education, it is very much necessary to identify the basic creativity inherent in the child and to nourish it. The responsibility to identify it is of a teacher. He has to discover such students who remain at the front-position in all the fields of life. And the researcher strictly believes that this work can very well be done by teacher at the school level. So, the researcher would honestly attempt to prepare an Aptitude (logical) Test for the students of commerce and management faculty.

2. Title of the study

A study of administrative aptitude of head teachers of primary school

3. Statement of the Problem

Gujarat government presently look forward and organizes various programme for the quality enhancement in primary education in accordance with Right to Education and norms of National Council of Teacher Education and Head teacher of primary school has been upgraded and selected as the 'Principal' in the primary education, in this situation it becomes necessary to study of Personality of Head Teacher of primary school appointed by the HTAT Examination at primary level.

4. Operational definition

In this present study statement of the is defined and to elaborate and focusing on the research study

what will be the study will be carried out by its meaning is explored through the operational definitions.

4.1 Primary School

According to the Act of Mumbai Primary Education-1947; Primary school means the school giving primary education of standard one (1) to seven (7). In this present study Primary School means school giving primary education of standard one (1) to eight (8) in Gujarat state according to the RTE-2009.

4.2 Jooth Shala (Group School)

According to GCERT cluster school that leads the school of the nearest seven or more than seven school of area availability of the frequency of the primary teacher.

5. Objectives of the study

To construct and standardize Principal Administrative Rating Scale for the Head Teacher of primary school.

- 1.To construct and standardize Administrative Aptitude Rating Scale for Head Teacher of primary school.
- 2.To study Administrative Aptitude traits of Head Teacher of primary school with reference to gender.
- 3.To study Administrative Aptitude traits of Head Teacher of primary school with reference to habitat.
- 4.To study Administrative Aptitude traits of Head Teacher of primary school with reference to educational Qualification Stream.
- 5.To study Administrative Aptitude traits of Head Teacher of primary school with reference to administrative experience and administrative experience.

6. Variables of the study

Variables are the conditions or characteristics that the experimenter manipulates, controls or observes. The following variables were considered in the present study. According to Deepika Shah: “Variable is one of the characteristics that be given value in which reflection characteristics can be seen in individual, group and environment. In this present study Head Teacher in primary school were considered as the control variable of the study. Variables of the present study are given as follows.

Table 1: Variables of the study

Sr.	Types of variables	Variable	Level	Information
	Independent	Gender	1.Male 2.Female	Collected Information
		Habitat	1.Rural 2.Urban	Collected Information
		Administrative experience	1.Exp. < 5 Years 2.Exp. > 5 Years	Collected Information
2.	Dependent	Administrative Aptitude		Administrative Aptitude Scale

7. Field of Research

In this present study newly appointed Head teacher of primary school has been upgraded and selected as the ‘Principal’ in the primary education by the Gujarat government for the quality enhancement in primary education. Head Teacher are considered as the field of the research of the study.

8. Types of Research

Research is looking scientific meaningful solution of problems. Present study descriptive type of the research was carried out. Descriptive research used to find out the new knowledge, truth, principle or generalization in new or unknown condition of life.

9. Limitation of Research

Every research could not be always comprehensive. Present research has some the limitation decided with reference to limitation of the research study. In this present research limitation of the present study are given as follows.

- Present study was delimited only Head Teacher of primary school of who are newly appointed on the basis of HTAT Examination of primary level. Present study was delimited only Head Teacher serving in the primary school of Gujarat during the year of 2019-2020.

10. Significance of Research

Research is one of the specific activities, which is useful and important in the field of education. Educational administrative problems can be solving by the using scientific way research. So, research work is very important. Significance of the present research is follows. Present research was useful to principals of the primary, secondary, higher secondary and the entire educational field at global level and it were useful to study the research studies at national and international level to study the problems of principals. As well as research work were helpful to organization like NCERT, GCERT, DIET to organize various training to the Head Teacher of the primary school of Gujarat State.

11. Research design

Research method is one of the parts of research. To distinguish the efforts between the specifying the research problem and outcomes of the study is known as the research method. Present research is descriptive type in nature. In the descriptive type research relational survey and developmental researches are used. In this present research survey method were used to collect the data.

12. Population and sample

In this present study all the Head Teacher in primary school of the Gujarat State were considered as the population of the study.

13. Selection of the sample

A sample may be defined as a selected number from the population to represent it. Generally, this selection is done according to some rule or plan. For the present study random sampling technique were used to taking sample for the research. In this present study total selected districts of Gujarat state and Head teachers were selected by the random sampling for the research purpose. From the present selected fourteen district total 4537 Head Teacher in primary school of the Gujarat State were consider as the sample of the study. By using lottery system one thousand Head Teacher of primary school were selected randomly.

Table 2: Gender wise sample

Gender	Sample
Male	285
Female	75
Total	360

From the Table, is shows that 285 and 75 male and female Head teachers of the primary schools from the North Gujarat were selected for the present study.

14. Tool for the study

Likert type, five-point scale of Administrative Aptitude Scale was prepared by the Investigator to keep in mind the Administrative Aptitude traits of Head Teachers in the primary school. Positive and negative items were selected and organized in the tool, total necessary items were tested and items were selected for the final try out of the study, finally standardization of tool were carried out by testing reliability and validity of the tool. Statements related to tool were collected and prepared by interviewing the experts and principals.

15. Hypothesis of the study

Hypothesis of the present study are given as follows.

- H₀₁:** There will be no significant difference between mean score of sample of male and female Primary school Head Teachers on Administrative Aptitude Rating Scale.
- H₀₂:** There will be no significant difference between mean score of sample of rural habitat and urban habitat Primary school Head Teachers on Administrative Aptitude Rating Scale.
- H₀₃:** There will be no significant difference between mean score of sample having less than 5 years and greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers on Administrative Aptitude Rating Scale.

16. Data Collection

In this present study to study the by the Head Teacher in primary school of the Gujarat State, prior permission will be taken from the newly appointed Head Teachers with the help of telephonic communication and then after letter and data were collected through administration of the tool by direct administrating Administrative Aptitude Scale.

17. Data analysis

As the need of the present study data were analyzed with reference to gender, habitat, education stream, category, educational qualification, teaching and administrative experience of Head Teacher of primary school. data were collected and analyzed by using score on tool and with the help of computer Mean, Mode, S.D., Chi-Square Value and t-Value, statistical technique applied to different group of sample for the present study.

18. Major findings of the study

Gender-wise Score of the percentage of frequency of the male and female sample of the Head teachers of the primary schools were found Very Low Administrative Aptitude (180-185) are 3 % and 7 % respectively same as Very High Administrative Aptitude (228-233) are 5 % and 5 % respectively on the Administrative Aptitude Rating Scale. Gender wise percentage of male is found higher than the Male Head teachers of the primary schools.

18.1 Effect of Gender, Habitat and experience of Primary School Head Teachers on Administrative Aptitude

18.1.1 Effect of Gender of Primary School Head Teachers on Administrative Aptitude

- Administrative Aptitude of male urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of female urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that gender-wise Administrative Aptitude of male Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than female Primary School Head Teachers.
- Administrative Aptitude of male having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of female having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that gender-wise Administrative Aptitude of male Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than female Primary School Head Teachers.
- Administrative Aptitude of male having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of female having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that gender-wise Administrative Aptitude of male Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than female Primary School Head Teachers.
- Administrative Aptitude of male rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of female rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that gender-wise Administrative Aptitude of male Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than female Primary School Head Teachers.

18.1.2 Effect of Habitat of Primary School Head Teachers on Administrative Aptitude

- Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat male Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of urban habitat male Head Teachers. So, it can be said that habitat-wise Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers.
- Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat female Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of urban habitat female Head Teachers. So, it can be said that habitat-wise Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers.
- Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of urban habitat having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that habitat-wise Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers.
- Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of urban habitat having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that habitat-wise Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers.
- Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that habitat-wise Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than urban habitat Primary School Head Teachers.

18.1.3 Effect of Experience of Primary School Head Teachers on Administrative Aptitude

- Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of rural habitat having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that experience-wise Administrative Aptitude of Primary School Head Teachers having greater than 5 years administrative experience were found to be significantly higher than Primary School Head Teachers having less than 5 years administrative experience.
- Administrative Aptitude of urban habitat having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of urban habitat having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that experience-wise Administrative Aptitude of Primary School Head Teachers having greater than 5 years administrative experience were found to be significantly higher than Primary School Head Teachers having less than 5 years administrative experience.
- Administrative Aptitude of male having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of male having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that experience-wise Administrative Aptitude of Primary School Head Teachers having greater than 5 years administrative experience were found to be significantly higher than Primary School Head Teachers having less than 5 years administrative experience.
- Administrative Aptitude of female having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of female having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So, it can be said that experience-wise Administrative Aptitude of Primary School Head Teachers having greater than 5 years administrative experience were found to be significantly higher than Primary School Head Teachers having less than 5 years administrative experience.

- Administrative Aptitude of having greater than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than the Administrative Aptitude of having less than 5 years administrative experience Primary School Head Teachers. So it can be said that experience-wise Administrative Aptitude of Primary School Head Teachers having greater than 5 years administrative experience were found to be significantly higher than Primary School Head Teachers having less than 5 years administrative experience.

19. Conclusion

From the above research it can be conclude that percentage of group of Male Head teachers of the primary schools were found higher than above female groups, percentage of group of Experience wise percentage of Head teachers of the primary schools having experience greater than 5 years were found higher than above other groups, there is effect of gender and experience of Primary School Head Teachers were found significant on Administrative Aptitude. gender-wise Administrative Aptitude of male Primary School Head Teachers were not found to be significantly higher than female Primary School Head Teachers, experience-wise Administrative Aptitude of Primary School Head Teachers having greater than 5 years administrative experience were found to be significantly higher than Primary School Head Teachers having less than 5 years administrative experience there is no any effect of habitat on Administrative Aptitude.

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